

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

AGGREGATION STATUS OF FOUR NIGERIAN SOIL CLASSES TESTED UNDER DIFFERENT WATER SOAKING TIME

Nweke I.,

Department of Soil Science Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Anambra State

Ijeh A.,

Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe, Anambra State, Nigeria

Okafor J.,

Department of Soil and Land Resource Management, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra, Nigeria

Ngonadi E.,

Department of Crop Science and Horticulture Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University

Igili D.

Department of Crop Science and Horticulture Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997208>

Abstract

The effect of soil texture and time of soaking on aggregate stability of four major soil textural classes in southeast, Nigeria was evaluated. Both the wet and dry sieving techniques were used for the study. Result findings indicated mean weight diameter (MWD) of clay loam texture to be significantly lowest in wet sieving compared to other texture classes. Period of soaking showed non-significant effect with all the indices used. Mean weight diameter dry (MWDD) correlated with mean weight diameter wet (MWDW), degree of aggregation (DA) and state of aggregation (SA), negatively at time 0, 30, 60, 90 and 120 minutes respectively. The correlation was significant at $P < 0.05$ with MWDW and DA at times 0 minutes. At time 30 minutes, it was significant at $P < 0.05$ with DA, while at time 90 minutes it was significant with MWDW. At time 120 minutes MWDD correlated significantly ($P < 0.05$) with MWDW, DA and SA. These results showed that the period of soaking had some contributions to the stability of soil aggregates especially with the trend in the correlation matrix between MWD dry and MWD wet, DA and SA.

Keywords: Aggregation, mean weight diameter, soaking, stability indices, texture

1. Introduction

Soil texture, an inherent property of soil, play a great role in the physical and chemical properties of soils. Its variation in nature brings about variation in soil properties, crop growth and yield and changes in environment. Soil texture is the center of activities and can give spatial picture of the soil parent material and micro climate of the soil area. Zhao et al. (2007) reported that soil properties vary spatially in nature because of variation in soil parent materials and microclimate. Soil texture can vary across agricultural soils and easily influence spatial variability in crop yields. Thus, texture can indicate or show the similarity of parent material and homogeneity of soil forming processes. This of which can be accelerated in southeast, Nigeria by weathering as a result of continue disturbance during farm management practices, intense rainfall and temperature. Textural class type can result from selective removal of clay particles by erosion, thereby increasing the proportion of the coarser particles in the soil, leaving more sand particles. Though the texture of a soil may not be affected in a short-term period, every activity in agricultural fields ranging from cultivation (especially intensive), organic/inorganic amendment, implement in use, harvest and all other farm and soil management practices therein can have a pronounce effect on the texture of a soil. Aggregation is very much associated with soil texture and its mineralogical composition. Increased clay dispersion with OM mineralization can decrease the macro and micro aggregates stability

of soils. Six et al. (2000), Deneff and Six (2005) and Norton (2006) found aggregate stability of soils to have varied and dependent on the associated minerals. The aggregation status of a textural class subjected to series of disturbances can show reduction in pore spaces, soil properties, carrying capacity and total collapse in soil aggregates in their contact. Nweke (2014) found collapse in the aggregation and carrying capacity of four cultivated soils of southeastern, Nigeria. Micro aggregate formation is important for the storage and stabilization of SOC in the long term (Gale et al., 2000). Increased activities in agricultural fields by cultivation and other management practices can reduce the binding forces between the soil aggregates especially in soils with low clay content such as southeastern soils of Nigeria. This has the capacity to cause leaching and erosion that wash away the soil binding agents and render the soil very weak to carry loads leading to the collapse of the soil (Neaman, 2000; Neaman and Singer 2000; Nweke, 2014). Thus, the development of stable soil aggregation is very crucial to ameliorate any soil problem that might arise from wet and dry behavior of soils, that may impose restriction to effective cultivation and crop production. Mbagwu (1992) found positive correlation between aggregate silt + clay index with all the macro indices, but water stable aggregate $< 0.25\text{mm}$ index had a negative correlation with all the macro aggregation indices. Also, Igwe and Stahr (2004) reported significant positive correlation between WSA (2.00 -

1.00mm) and WSA (1.000 - 0.50mm), total clay content and silt + clay contents. While Nweke and Nnabude (2015a) found that the contributions between OC, silt + clay fractions and aggregate stability was small and non-significant.

Many methods for assessing soil structural stability have been developed and adopted. However, beyond all methods dry and wet sieving techniques have been found generally applicable to all soils. This technique has the ability to offset or minimize the cumbersome assessment and time-consuming aggregate size distribution analysis. Nweke, (2000), Nweke and Nnabude, (2014, 2015ab), Burkke et al. (1986) used dry and wet sieving methods for direct soil structural stability assessment. Chisco et al. (1989) passed the soil through a 4mm mesh and immersed with distilled water for 10 minutes on the top of a nest of sieves of diameter 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.25mm. The nest of sieves was then vertically oscillated in water with stroke of 4cm for a time period long enough to have a relatively constant mass of particles in each sieve and the same procedure also is used in the single sieve analysis. Matkin and Smart, (1987) used 50 grams of air-dry soil 3.35-5.60mm aggregates immersed for 30 minutes in excess tap water and then sieved by machine through 2mm and 0.5mm sieves for 100 strokes both sieves being immersed into and lifted clear of the water on each stroke. Conway and stickling (1962) on the other hand used 25g soil sample spread on the top sieve of a nest of sieves (2.0mm and 0.5mm) and the nest was immersed and allowed to soak for 5 minutes and then sieved for 2 minutes. The soil was completely submerged during immersion and wet sieving. Also, Obi (1990) allowed the aggregates to immerse for 5 minutes before running the aggregate machine for 2 minutes. Piccolo and Mbagwu (1994) pre-immersed 20g of treated aggregate for 30 minutes on a 0.5mm sieve, then vertically oscillated 20 times at a rate of one oscillation per second. Also Piccolo and Mbagwu (1999), pre-immersed in water for 30 minutes using 20g of soil placed on the top most of a nest of four sieves with diameter of 2.00, 1.00 0.50 and 0.25mm. Nweke, (2000) and Adesondum et al. (2001), placed on top most of a nest of sieves 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.25mm 40g soil sample of < 5mm aggregates and pre-immersed in distilled water for 10 minutes before oscillating vertically in water for 20 minutes. From the highlighted literatures, the highest time so far used for pre-immersion or immersion before sieving is 30 minutes but precipitation sometimes could even be more in a tropical environment. Some agricultural fields in southeast, Nigeria is capable of holding water for hours before the water drains off. This will have effect on the stability of aggregates on the field. To investigate this field conditions using wet and dry sieving methods, four major textural classes of soil in the southeast, Nigeria were selected for the study namely; clay loam, sandy clay loam, loam and sandy loam with the aim to determine the effect of texture on aggregate stability, variation of aggregate stability with period of immersion and to relate aggregate stability indices to selected soil physicochemical properties.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sampling and Site Description

Four locations in southeast, Nigeria were chosen and sampled for this study. The locations distinguished by textural class include; Ihiala, Omor, Lilu and Nsukka area. At each location soil samples were taken with a soil auger at the 0-20cm depth and put in air tight polythene bag. Three samples each serving as a replicate were collected from each soil textural class. The area within each location from which the soil samples were collected are;

Amamputu in Uli across Ogada River in Ihiala local government area of Anambra state and Farm W7 an experimental farm at Anambra lower river basin are the two locations from which loam (L) texture soil for the study was collected. The area is located on latitude 06°8'N and longitude 07°2'E.

The experimental plot, Turn-out W4 and turn-out W8 (CRW4) in lower Anambra irrigation project field at Omor was where the clay loam (CL) textured soil was collected. The project is located on latitude 06°3' and longitude 07°0'E

At Umuzu and Near Ugwuakukor, River Lilu, located on latitude 06°20'N and longitude 07°12'E, with an average annual rainfall of about 1500-2000mm is where sandy loam textured soil was collected.

Nsukka is the next location from which the sandy clay loam (SCL) was collected. It was collected from the University of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN) Agricultural farm. Nsukka is located on latitude 06°52'N and longitude 07°24'E within the derived savanna zone of southeast, Nigeria. More than 85% of its annual rainfall of 1550mm falls within the raining season. The soil is characterized by rapid to very rapid permeability as a result of high percentage of sand.

Also, in each of the location three (3) undisturbed soil core samples were taken and used to determine bulk density (BD) and pore size distribution, that is micro-macro pore; total porosity (TP) and hydraulic conductivity (HC).

2.2. Laboratory methods

2.2.1. Chemical Properties

The cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soils was obtained by the extraction method of Jackson (1958).

Walkley and Black (1934) method was used to determine organic carbon content of the soils.

Exchangeable sodium was measured from ammonium acetate leachate using the flame photometer.

2.2.2. Physical properties

Particle size analysis was measured by the Bouyoucos (1951) hydrometer method while core method described by the Blake (1986) was used to determine the Bulk density.

Water retention method was used to determine the pore size distribution while total porosity was estimated from bulk density and particle density using the formula;

$$TP = 1 - \frac{BD}{PD} \times 100 \text{ ----- equation 1}$$

Where BD = Bulk density, PD = Particle density

The modified constant water head methods of Klute (1986) was used to measure Hydraulic conductivity.

$$K = \frac{Q \times dz}{A \times t \times dh} \text{ ----- equation 2}$$

Where K= saturated hydraulic conductivity cm s^{-1}

Q = the steady state volume flow from entire volume cm^3/hr

dz = length of core sampler (cm)

A = cross section area (cm^2)

t = change in time interval (hr)

dh = hydraulic head change (cm)

Core samples of length 5cm and 5.6 cm diameters were used with hydraulic head changes of 2.5 cm.

2.3. Aggregate Stability

$$\text{DSA1 (> 2.00 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of dry aggregates on 2.00 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 3}$$

$$\text{DSA 2 (2.00 mm – 1.00 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of dry aggregates on 1.00 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 4}$$

$$\text{DSA 3 (1.00 mm – 0.5 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of dry aggregates on 0.5 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 5}$$

$$\text{DSA 4 (0.5 mm – 0.25 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of dry aggregates on 0.25 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 6}$$

$$\text{DSA 5 (< 0.25 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of dry aggregates passed on through 0.25 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 7}$$

$$\text{Dry mean weight diameter (MWDD)} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i w_i \text{ ----- equation 8}$$

Where n = total number of size

x = the arithmetic mean diameter of each size fraction

i = sieve opening (mm)

w = the proportion of the total weight occurring in each size grade

2.3.2. Wet sieve aggregate

40g of soil samples (< 4.75mm) from each of the textures was placed on the topmost sieve of the nest of sieves and pre- soaked at different periods and then oscillated for 2 minutes. The samples remaining in each of the sieves were collected dried and weighed. After weighing and recording the soil samples they were

2.3.3. Water stable aggregates (WSA)

$$\text{WSA 1 (> 2.0 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of aggregates on 2.0 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 9}$$

$$\text{WSA 2 (2.0 mm – 1.0 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of aggregates on 1.0 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 10}$$

$$\text{WSA 3 (1.0 mm – 0.5mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of aggregates on 0.5 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 11}$$

$$\text{WSA 4 (0.5mm – 0.25 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of aggregates on 0.25 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 12}$$

$$\text{WSA 5 (< 0.25 mm)} = \frac{\text{wt of aggregates that passed through the 0.25 mm sieve} \times 100}{\text{initial weight of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 13}$$

2.3.4. Mean Weight Diameter wet aggregates (MWDW)

$$\text{MWDW} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i w_i \text{ ----- equation 14}$$

Where n = total number of size

x_i = the sum of the product of the means diameter of each size fraction

w_i = proportion of the total sample weight w_i of each size fraction

MWDW = Mean weight diameter of wet aggregates (mm)

2.3.5. State of aggregation (SA)

$$\text{SA} = \frac{\text{wt of water stable aggregate} - \text{wt of sand} \times 100}{\text{wt of sample}} \text{ ----- equation 15}$$

2.3.6. Degree of aggregation (DA)

$$\text{DA} = \frac{\text{wt of water stable aggregate} - \text{wt of sand} \times 100}{\text{wt of sample} - \text{wt of sand}} \text{ ----- equation 16}$$

This was determined using wet and dry sieving method of Yoder (1936). The principle involved the use of sieves with diameters 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.25mm. The time of soaking /pre- soaking selected were; 0 minutes, 30 minutes, 60 minutes, 90 minutes and 120 minutes, the textural class evaluated were sandy loam, sandy clay loam, clay loam and loam.

2.3.1. Dry sieve aggregate (DSA)

The dry sieving was done using the FRITSCH laboratory shaker (Germany) to shake the 40g soil sample placed on top of a set of sieves, arranged in their descending order of 2.00 mm, 1.00 mm, and 0.5 mm, 0.25 mm and dry stable aggregates DSA1 to DSA5 were obtained with the formula stated below;

bulked together and soaked for 24 hours in NaOH. The sand was then washed through a 0.5 mm sieve into an evaporating dish. The water was decanted and the sand oven dried for at least 24 hours and weighed. This was repeated with the 3 replications of the textures used. The following aggregate stability indices were determined:

2.4. Experimental Design

The study was arranged as a factorial (4x5x3) experiment in complete randomized design (CRD) where factor A is the four (4) soil textural classes and factor B

is the five (5) different soaking /pre-soaking time with three (3) replications. The Table 1 below show twenty (20) treatment combinations of the soil textures and soaking /pre- soaking time.

Table 1

Treatment combinations of the soil textures and soaking /pre- soaking time

Factor A	A1	A2	A3	A4
Factor B				
B1	A1B1	A2B1	A3B1	A4B1
B2	A1B2	A2B2	A3B2	A4B2
B3	A1B3	A2B3	A3B3	A4B3
B4	A1B4	A2B4	A3B4	A4B4
B5	A1B5	A2B5	A3B5	A4B5

Factor A = Soil texture

A1 = Sandy loam (SL)

A2 = Sandy clam loam (SCL)

A3 = Loam (L)

A4 = Clay loam (CL)

Factor B = soaking /pre- soaking time.

B1 = 0 minutes of soaking /pre- soaking time

B2 = 30 minutes of soaking /pre- soaking time

B3 = 60 minutes of soaking /pre- soaking time

B4 = 90 minutes of soaking /pre- soaking time

B5 = 120 minutes of soaking /pre- soaking time

Table 2

Final ANOVA Table

Source	Degree of Freedom	Value
Treatment combination	AB-1	19
Factor A	A-1	3
Factor B	B-1	4
Interaction AB	(A-1)(B-1)	12
Error	AB(R-1)	40
Total	ABR-1	59

2.5. Data Analysis

Data generated from the study were analyzed using the ANOVA test. Separation of treatment means for statistical significance was done by the least significant difference (LSD) at 5 % alpha level. Multiple correlation analysis was used to compare dry and wet sieving techniques at various soaking /pre- soaking time periods with the four soil textural classes and relating the aggregate stability indices to selected soil properties.

3. Results.

The result presented in Table 3 showed the characterization of the soil samples collected. Across the locations from which the soil samples were collected

sand was found to be the dominant fraction. And it varies with the location with highest to least order of Lilu (226%) > Nsukka (176%) > Ihiala (145%) > Omor (99%). Among all the location, Omor has the highest clay (88%) and silt (112%) fractions, while the least 37% clay and silt respectively found in Lilu. The fractions equally varied with replications. Ijeh's compound Lilu, replication (rep) I indicated highest (76%) sand fraction and least (11%) in silt fraction among all the replications. The next in rank is Ugwuakukor rep 2 and 3 that had the same sand fraction of 75% and least silt fraction of 12% in Ugwuakukor rep 2. The least clay (11%) fraction relative to all the replication and locations was obtained from Ugwuakukor rep. 3.

Table 3

Percentage (%) sand, silt and clay of the soil textures used

S/N	LOCATION	REPLICATION	TOTAL SAND	% CLAY	% SILT	TEXTURAL CLASS
1	Poultry section UNN	1	56	30	14	Sandy clay Loam (SCL)
2	Poultry section UNN	2	55	29	16	Sandy clay Loam (SCL)
3	Meterology section UNN	3	60	23	17	Sandy clay loam (SCL)
4	Ijeh's Compound Umuzu, Lilu	1	76	13	11	Sandy loamy (SL)
5	Near Ugwuakukor stream Lilu	2	75	13	12	Sandy loam (SL)
6	Near Ugwuakukor stream Lilu	3	75	11	14	Sandy loam (SL)
7	CRW 4, W8 Anambra Lower River Basin Omor, Oyi LGA	1	35	32	33	Clay loam (CL)
8	Turn out W4 Anambra Lower River Basin Omor Oyi L.G.A	2	33	29	38	Clay loam (CL)
9.	CRW4, W5 Anambra Lower River Basin Omor, Oyi LGA	3	31	27	42	Clay loam (CL)
10	Amamputu Ogada 1 Uli	1	45	23	32	Loam (L)
11	Amamputu Ogada 4 Uli	2	43	21	36	Loam (L)
12	Exp. Farm W7 Anambra Lower Basin Omor Oyi L.G.A	3	57	20	29	Loam (L)

3.1. Physicochemical characterization of the soils used for the study.

The laboratory description of the soil samples used is presented in Table 4. The result showed that both the physical and chemical properties of the soil varied with both texture and replication. The BD showed the least value in rep 3 of loam texture relative to all other soil textures and replications. The BD result of the soil textures showed a variation of SCL > C > SL > L. The least and highest value of total porosity (TP) and field capacity (FC) was obtained from SCL (42.2%; 27.0%) and L (54.90%; 43.90%) respectively. The micro pore (MD) and macro pore (MP) showed result variation of SCL > L > CL > SL (MD) and SL > L > SCL > CL (MP) respectively. MP value in CL is very small with a value

of 7.47% of which the percentage decrease in value relative to SL value is 160.11%. Clay loam (CL) soil recorded the least (1.63 cmhr⁻¹) value of HC relative to other soils, next in rank to the least is loam (L) soil that recorded 8.00cmhr⁻¹ of HC, while the highest (34.43cmhr⁻¹) value was obtained from sandy loam (SL). The recorded value for OC and OM content of the soils is of low value and showed result variation of L > CL > SL > SCL, though for OC content CL and SL recorded the same value 0.33%. The CEC content of the soils were of medium value and varied from 4.67 cmolkg⁻¹ recorded in SCL to 8.80 cmolkg⁻¹ recorded from loam (L) soil. The exchangeable Na of the soils is of low value of which the least 0.27 cmolkg⁻¹ was recorded in SL and the highest 0.43 cmolkg⁻¹ was obtained from SCL

Table 4

Physicochemical characterization of the soils used for the study

Location/town	Texture	Replication	BD gcm ⁻³	HC cmhr ⁻¹	TP %	FC %	MD %	MP %	OC %	OM %	CEC cmolkg ⁻¹	Na cmolkg ⁻¹
Ihiala	Loam	1	1.3	3.1	51.7	37.6	33.0	18.7	0.8	1.4	8.4	0.2
		2	1.2	3.4	57.0	45.8	41.9	14.7	0.8	1.4	4.0	0.4
		3	1.1	17.5	56.0	48.3	47.6	9.4	0.2	0.3	14.0	0.3
Lilu	Sandy loam	1	1.4	46.7	45.7	21.8	21.2	24.1	0.2	0.4	4.4	0.4
		2	1.4	20.1	46.4	37.5	34.8	11.6	0.6	1.0	6.8	0.0
		3	1.3	36.5	49.8	29.6	27.2	22.6	0.2	0.3	6.0	0.4
Omor	Clay loam	1	1.4	1.0	48.7	38.8	43.7	5.0	0.3	0.6	6.8	0.4
		2	1.5	1.0	41.9	34.5	33.4	8.5	0.3	0.6	5.6	0.3
		3	1.3	2.9	50.9	41.6	42.0	8.9	0.4	0.7	9.6	0.3
Nsukka	Sandy clay loam	1	1.5	17.5	43.4	28.5	32.3	11.1	0.2	0.3	3.6	0.4
		2	1.4	17.0	47.2	26.1	36.1	11.1	0.2	0.3	4.0	0.4
		3	1.7	9.2	36.2	28.5	62.3	10.2	0.1	0.2	6.4	0.5

BD = Bulk density, HC = Hydraulic conductivity, TP = Total porosity, FC = Field capacity, MD = Micro-pore; MP = Macro-pore; OC = Organic carbon; OM = Organic matter; CEC = Cation exchange capacity; Na = Exchangeable Sodium

3.2. Effect of soil texture on aggregate stability indices as determined by wet sieving technique.

The result of aggregate stability indices as influenced by soil texture recorded in Table 5, showed that the MWD obtained by wet sieving from CL was significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower than the values obtained from the other soil textures, while others were not statistically different (Table 5). The water stable aggregates WSA1 ($> 2.00\text{mm}$), WSA2 ($2.00\text{-}1.00\text{mm}$), WSA3 ($1.00\text{-}0.5\text{mm}$), WSA4 ($0.500\text{mm} - 0.25\text{mm}$), SA and DA gave similar result as MWD in that their significant lower values were recorded in clay loam (CL). Their

values were also observed to be varied significantly ($P < 0.05$) strongly with the soil texture by the virtue of their recorded values different from one another. In WSA5 ($< 0.25\text{mm}$) the obtained value with respect to the various soil textures were very significantly different from one another. Highest value (62.4) was recorded from clay loam (CL) among all the soil textures as against lower values recorded by the other parameters in that particular soil texture (CL). The value of WSA4 obtained showed the values from SCL and SL; SL and L; L and CL to be statistically similar.

Table 5

Main effect of texture on aggregate stability indices as determine by wet sieving technique

Texture	MWDW	WSA 1 > 2.00mm	WSA 2 2.00- 1.00mm	WSA 3 1.00 - 0.5mm	WSA 4 0.5 - 0.25mm	WSA 5 < 0.25mm	SA	DA
Loam (L)	1.1	19.7	15.0	15.9	16.4	32.9	40.8	46.7
Sandy loam (SL)	1.3	26.9	15.9	12.4	18.2	26.5	45.7	49.8
Clay Loam (CL)	0.6	9.4	7.3	7.9	12.9	62.4	16.2	19.7
Sandy clay loam (SCL)	1.4	26.1	17.3	20.4	20.5	15.8	47.9	55.4
LSD (0.05)	0.31	9.58	2.55	3.06	3.96	7.31	10.59	10.50

MWDW = Mean weight diameter wet; SA = State of Aggregation; DA = Degree of aggregation; L = Loam; SL = Sandy loam; CL = Clay loam; SCL = Sandy clay loam; WSA = Water stable aggregates

3.3. Effect of soil texture on aggregate stability indices as evaluated by dry sieving technique.

The MWDD values (Table 6) obtained with respect to the various textures were statistically ($P < 0.05$) different from each other except the recorded values in SL and SCL; loam and CL respectively that are not statistically different from one another. The value of MWDD recorded with respect to CL and L were higher than the values obtained from the other soil textures. The DSA1 ($> 2.00\text{mm}$) and DSA2 ($2.00\text{-}1.00\text{mm}$) gave similar result as MWDD. The dry stable aggregate DSA2 ($2\text{-}1.00\text{mm}$) showed significant difference among the soil textures studied, but the recorded values from SL, CL and SCL; L and CL showed statistically

similar result and non-significant. Dry stable aggregate DSA3 ($1.00\text{mm} - 0.5\text{mm}$) value was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) different with sandy clay loam (SCL), while other soil textures were not statistically different. Dry stable aggregate DSA4 ($0.5 - 0.25\text{mm}$) value obtained from L and CL showed statistically similar result, but values of SL and SCL were statistically ($P < 0.05$) different from the values of L and CL textures. The DSA5 ($< 0.25\text{mm}$) value obtained from SL was highest (60.4) and showed statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) different relative to the other soil textures. The other soil textures of L, CL and SCL were not different from each other statistically (Table 6).

Table 6

Main effect of texture on aggregate stability indices as evaluated by dry sieving

Texture	MWDD	DSA 1 > 2.00mm	DSA 2 2.00mm-1.00mm	DSA 3 1.00mm-0.5mm	DSA 4 0.5mm-0.25mm	DSA 5 > 0.25mm
L	2.2	59.1	9.9	2.5	2.2	26.4
SL	0.3	1.6	2.6	6.5	28.6	60.4
CL	2.4	65.4	6.9	2.6	2.7	22.4
SCL	0.4	1.2	4.4	23.0	32.4	38.8
LSD(0.05)	0.58	19.10	5.01	9.50	3.11	19.17

MWDD = Mean weight diameter dry; DSA = Dry sieving stable aggregates; L = Loam; SL = Sandy loam; CL = Clay loam; SCL = Sandy clay loam;

3.4. Aggregate stability evaluated under different period of soaking.

The effect of period of soaking on the aggregate stability indices used in the study showed non-significant different among the period considered (Table 7). The highest MWD of 1.4 was recorded in 0 minutes relative to the other soil textures. The data generated showed the values to be independent of the increment in minutes as in some cases they decrease as the minutes of soaking increased, while in some they increase as the minutes of soaking increased. However, if

the result is interpreted with the mean value of all the tested parameters, the effect of period of soaking on aggregate stability show a result variation of 0 minutes $>$ 60 minutes $>$ 120minutes $>$ 90minutes $>$ 30minutes. Higher value was recorded in each minutes considered with respect to WSA5 (< 0.025) relative to WSA1 - WSA4, while DA value in each minutes among all the parameters tested recorded the highest value followed by SA result.

Table 7

Main effect of period of soaking on aggregate stability indices

Time	MWD	WSA 1 >2.00mm	WSA 2 2.00mm- 1.00mm	WSA 3 1.00mm- 0.5mm	WSA 4 0.5mm- 0.25mm	WSA 5 <0.25mm	SA	DA	Mean
0 min.	1.4	29.7	13.7	11.9	15.0	29.8	43.7	48.4	24.3
30 min	1.0	16.7	15.3	15.2	18.1	34.7	35.7	40.0	22.06
60 min	1.1	19.1	15.4	14.7	16.7	36.3	36.7	45.4	22.91
90 min	1.1	20.4	12.2	14.8	17.2	35.5	36.1	40.3	22.20
120min	1.1	18.7	13.0	14.5	18.0	35.8	36.3	40.3	22.3
LSD0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	

MWD = Mean weight diameter; WSA = Water stable aggregates; NS = Not significant; SA = State of aggregation; DA = Degree of aggregation

3.5. Correlation coefficient of aggregate stability indices tested.

The relationship of aggregate stability indices used presented in Table 8 showed WSA1 to correlate highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) and positive with WSA2 and MWD with r values of 0.393 and 0.976 respectively while it correlates highly significant ($P < 0.01$) and negative with WSA5, r value -0.695 and negatively at $P < 0.05$ with WSA4, r value -0.306. Its correlation with WSA3 showed negative and not statistically significant. The water stable aggregate 2.00mm - 1.00mm (WSA2) had highly significant ($P < 0.01$) positive correlation with WSA3, WSA4 and MWD, but negative

and highly significant ($P < 0.01$) with WSA5 their r values are; 0.542, 0.347, 0.565 and - 0.8.9 respectively. WSA3 correlated highly significant ($P < 0.01$) and positive with WSA4 but negatively and highly significant ($P < 0.01$) with WSA5 with r values of 0.794 and - 0.575 respectively. Its correlation coefficient with MWD though positive was not statistically significant. Water stable aggregate 0.5mm - 0.25mm (WSA4) had negative and highly significant correlation with WSA5 with r value of - 0.397 but negative and non-statistically significant correlation with MWD. WSA5 < 0.25mm correlated negatively and highly significant ($P < 0.01$) with MWD with r value of - 0.814.

Table 8

Correlation coefficient for the linear relationship between aggregate stability indices of water stable aggregates (WSA) and mean weight diameter (MWD)

	WSA1	WSA2	WSA3	WSA4	WSA5	MWDW
WSA1						
WSA2	0.393**					
WSA3	-0.134	0.542**				
WSA4	-0.306*	0.347**	0.794**			
WSA5	-0.695**	-0.809**	-0.575**	-0.397**		
MWDW	0.976**	0.565**	0.040 NS	-0.173 NS	-0.814	

** = highly significant (** $P < 0.01$); * = significant (* $P < 0.05$); NS = Not significant at $P < 0.05$

3.6. Linear relationship between aggregate stability indices; MWD, DA, SA, and MWDD at 0-120 minutes.

The correlation coefficient results in Table 9 showed that at 0 minutes MWDW had highly positive significant $P < 0.01$ correlation with DA and SA with r value of 0.929 and 0.863 respectively and negative significant correlation at $P < 0.05$ with MWDD, while DA correlated positively ($P < 0.01$) with SA and negatively with MWDD at $P < 0.5$ with r value of 0.976 and - 0.593 respectively. The correlation between SA and MWDD was found to be negative and not significant. The result of 30 minutes indicated MWDW to be correlated positively and highly significant ($P < 0.01$) with DA and SA r values, 0.938 and 0.880 respectively, but negatively and not significant with MWDD. The relationship between DA and SA at ($P < 0.01$) as well as MWDD at ($P < 0.05$) were positive and significant with r value of 0.972 and 0.639 respectively. SA and MWDD linear relationship was negative and statistically significant at $P < 0.05$ with r value of - 0.621. The 60 minutes' period of soaking showed MWDW to correlate positively at $P < 0.01$ with DA and SA r values,

0.832 and 0.864 respectively, but negative and non-significant with MWDD. DA result showed positive ($P < 0.01$) correlation with SA ($r = 0.769$) and negative but not significant correlation with MWDD. The result of 90 minutes' soaking showed positive ($P < 0.01$) and negative ($P < 0.05$) relationship between MWDW and DA ($r = 0.905$); SA ($r = 0.860$) and MWDD ($r = -0.607$) respectively. Positive and highly ($P < 0.01$) relationship was recorded between DA and SA r value is 0.986, but correlate negatively and non-significant with MWDD. The correlation coefficient of SA and MWDD was not statistically significant. The correlation coefficient result of 120 minutes showed statistically significant result in all the parameters considered. MWDW had highly positive and significant ($P < 0.01$) correlation with DA and SA with r value of 0.951 and 0.922 respectively and negative at $P < 0.05$ with MWDD with r value, -0.616. The DA correlated positively at $P < 0.01$ with SA ($r = 0.982$) and negatively at $P < 0.05$ with MWDD with r value - 0.607 respectively. While SA had negative and significant ($P < 0.05$) correlation with MWDD, r value -0.607. From the recorded result, it was observed that MWDW correlated significantly positive with DA and SA at every minutes of soaking

considered and significantly negative with MWDD except at 30 and 60 minutes that were not statistically significant. SA was not statistically significant with

MWDD in all the minutes of soaking except at 30 and 120 minutes where it correlated significantly ($P < 0.05$) negative.

Table 9

Linear relationship between MWDW, DA, SA and MWDD at time 0 to 120 minutes

0 minutes				
Parameter	MWDW	DA	SA	MWDD
MWDW	-			
DA	0.929**	-		
SA	0.863**	0.976**	-	
MWDD	-0.585*	-0.593*	-0.549 NS	-
30 minutes				
MWDW	-			
DA	0.938**	-		
SA	0.880**	0.972**	-	
MWDD	-0.551 NS	0.639*	-0.621*	-
60 minutes				
MWDW	-			
DA	0.832**	-		
SA	0.864**	0.769**	-	
MWDD	-0.504 NS	-0.396 NS	-0.568 NS	-
90 minutes				
MWDW	-			
DA	0.905**	-		
SA	0.860**	0.986**	-	
MWDD	-0.607*	-0.535 NS	-0.484 NS	-
120 minutes				
MWDW	-			
DA	0.951**	-		
SA	0.922**	0.982**	-	
MWDD	-0.616*	-0.651*	-0.607*	-

** significant at $P < 0.01$; * significant at $P < 0.05$; MWDW= mean weight diameter wet; MWDD = mean weight diameter dry; DA = degree of aggregation; SA = state of aggregation

3.7. Correlation coefficient between aggregate stability indices and soil physicochemical properties

The linear relationship between aggregate stability indices and soil properties is presented in Table 10. The result showed that at 0 minutes, the aggregate stability indices had no significant correlation with the tested soil parameters except for SA that correlated significantly ($P < 0.05$) and negatively with exchangeable Na ($r = -0.627$) and MWDD that correlated positively with

FC at $P < 0.01$ and TP at $P < 0.05$ with r value of 0.734 and 0.586 respectively and negatively at $P < 0.05$ with HC with r value -0.702. At 30 minutes the correlation result was similar to that of 60, 90 and 120 minutes' correlation results, where MWDD was found to correlate positively with FC at $P < 0.01$ and TP at $P < 0.05$ and negatively at $P < 0.05$ with HC incidentally their (30, 60, 90 and 120) r values at the considered parameters are the same.

Table 10

Linear relationship between aggregate stability indices and soil properties

parameter	BD gcm ⁻³	FC %	TP %	MD %	MP %	HC cmhr ⁻¹	OC %	CEC cmolkg ⁻¹	Exch. Na cmolkg ⁻¹
At time 0 minutes									
MWDW	0.147	-0.114	-0.140	0.145	0.310	0.405	-0.183	0.127	-0.538
DA	0.109	-0.151	-0.068	0.131	0.407	0.363	-0.011	0.020	-0.559
SA	0.127	-0.122	-0.060	0.155	0.358	0.227	0.144	-0.064	-0.627*
MWDD	0.523	0.734**	0.586*	0.215	-0.397	-0.702*	0.437	0.554	0.213
At time 30 minutes									
MWDW	0.169	-0.169	-0.179	0.315	0.081	0.255	-0.335	0.136	-0.432
DA	0.254	-0.304	-0.200	0.101	0.264	0.347	-0.225	-0.031	-0.480
SA	0.272	-0.315	-0.192	0.062	0.346	0.313	-0.079	-0.106	-0.555
MWDD	-0.532	0.734**	0.586*	0.215	-0.397	-0.702*	0.437	0.554	0.213
At time 60 minutes									
MWDW	0.450	-0.211	-0.432	0.213	0.021	0.036	-0.228	-0.147	-0.440
DA	0.116	0.025	-0.102	0.250	0.140	0.104	-0.111	0.160	-0.425
SA	0.331	-0.277	-0.256	0.017	0.350	0.140	0.126	-0.363	-0.485
MWDD	-0.532	0.734**	0.586*	0.215	-0.397	-0.702*	0.437	0.554	0.213
At time 90 minutes									
MWDW	0.150	-0.139	-0.158	-0.194	0.252	0.285	-0.152	-0.078	-0.409
DA	-0.015	-0.105	-0.039	0.063	0.273	0.170	0.084	-0.232	-0.271
SA	-0.084	-0.076	0.119	-0.020	-0.329	0.155	0.198	-0.255	-0.250
MWDD	-0.532	0.734**	0.586*	0.215	-0.397	-0.702*	0.437	0.554	0.213
At time 120 minutes									
MWDW	0.150	-0.226	-0.158	0.119	0.279	0.376	-0.317	0.000	0.301
DA	0.181	-0.275	-0.151	0.084	0.324	0.303	-0.138	-0.176	-0.353
SA	0.148	-0.239	-0.100	0.054	0.395	0.274	0.001	-0.200	-0.404
MWDD	-0.532	0.734**	0.586*	0.215	-0.397	-0.702*	0.437	0.554	0.213

** Significant at $P < 0.01$; * significant at $P < 0.05$; BD = bulk density; FC = field capacity; TP = total porosity; MD = micro porosity; MP = macro porosity; HC = hydraulic conductivity

4. Discussion

The dominant of sand fraction in the study probably reflect the parent material from which the soil classes were formed. The content of sand in the study ranges from 31-76% in all the soil class types. The dominant of sand may as well suggest that the parent material is of coastal plain sand. Systematic variation in soil texture class commonly occurs due to some factors such as vegetation cover, cultural practices, rate of water movement and storage, tillage, organic and inorganic applications, topography etc. In unprotected lands for instance, the finer soil particles will be selectively removed by erosion, this increases the proportion of sand particles. Also, deforestation, farming practices and intensive grazing change soil texture by aggravating soil erosion. Generally, the soil classes studied, showed soils of high permeability and porosity, moderate water and nutrient retention and transmission. The bulk density of the studied soil was observed to range from 1.1 - 1.7gcm⁻³. This result could be associated to low OM and less aggregation, and non-compaction from the impact of rain drops. Thus, poses no serious limitation to agricultural productivity. The FC, HC and TP values suggest soils with high water retention and transmission that will ensure continuous nutrient supply and absorption into crop tissues. The MD and MP results could be associated to the clay content of the textural class; thus, the dominance of the MD may have resulted from clay accumulation. Hence water retention will be higher in soils with high clay contents relative

to those with low clay content. The OC, OM, CEC and Na values were observed to be low. This simply suggest soils deficient in plant nutrients or leached soils, low nutrient recycling and cannot easily support crop production without amendment. All these will have various impacts on the soil aggregation status of the soils studied.

The reflection of the results obtained in all the aggregate stability indices evaluated by both wet and dry sieving techniques (Table 5 and 6) showed soil texture to be a significant ($P < 0.05$) factor controlling the aggregation and stability of aggregates. High fraction of large aggregates signifies a strong soil structure and a high resistance to water erosion; however, the highest fraction of aggregates was observed in <0.25mm (Table 5 and 6) and it is the only micro-aggregation index of all the indices used in this study. Its higher values indicated lower stability of the aggregate. The nature of the result obtained could be associated among other things with OM and mineralogical composition of the soil and cultivation activities as the soils are under different agricultural activities. Cultivation of the soil weakens the soil aggregates leading to reduction in the proportion of larger aggregates. Spaccini et al. (2005) reported that in Nigeria cultivation reduced the proportion of WSA between 6-61%. Albrech (1998) noted that when the contributions of Na and Mg to the cation exchange capacity of a soil exceed 30%, water stable macro-aggregates are rare and this type of soil like the studied soils are particularly susceptible to dispersion or disaggregation.

Among the soil textures the <0.25mm WSA of clay loam (CL) was observed to be highest (62.4) determined by wet sieving of which the percentage reduction in the other soil textures relative to clay loam (CL) value were; sandy clay loam (SCL) (74.68%) > sandy loam (SL) (57.53%) > loam (L) (47.28%) respectively. In the clay loam also, the percentage reduction variation in the WSA1-4 relative to <0.25mm is high, WSA1 (84.94%); WSA2 (88.30%); WSA3 (87.34%) and WSA4 (79.33%) respectively. These variations could be associated with OM content and clay mineralogy. The dry sieve method depicted SL to be highest value (60.4) in DSA5 and overall highest value (65.4) in the DSA was recorded in DSA1 of clay loam (CL). Del Galdo et al. (2003) and Nweke (2015) noted that OM is generally mixed with the mineral soil constituents to form soil aggregates. And OM content of the studied soils were low (Table 4). However, in highly weathered soil such as the studied soils clay mineralogy with iron oxides other than OM may be responsible for the stability of soil aggregates against disaggregation and collapse of aggregates (slaking). The result of soaking period was not significant on the stability of aggregate indices used. This indicates low contribution in the stability of aggregates. The wetting and dry cycles cause weak bonding between clay particles and the aggregates of WSA class 1-0.50mm (Zhang and Horn, 2001).

All the aggregate stability indices used correlated either positively or negatively with each other, soil properties and with time 0-120 minutes at $P < 0.01$ and/or $P < 0.05$ though some were not significant. The positive correlation indicated that as one of the aggregates correlated increased the other also increased while negative correlation indicates that as one of the aggregate index correlated increased the other decreased. Thus, the correlation coefficient showed clearly that relationship existed between the indices used, soil properties determined, period of soaking observed and aggregate stability. The correlation coefficient for the linear relationships especially between MWD wet and MWD dry showed strong indication of the contribution of soaking period to the stability of the soils. Water stability of micro-aggregate usually depends on OC binding agents; therefore, the results generally may be attributed to the OC content, differences in size of the aggregates and clay content of the soil textural class studied. Amezketa (1999) was of the opinion that aggregates of different sizes show different stability with the highest stability of the lower hierarchical order. The fact that aggregate stability indices used did not correlate with OC and CEC under observed period of soaking can be that the level of OC and clay content (Table 4 and 3) is low and percentage contribution of Na to CEC is very low to cause aggregation, hence disaggregation of the aggregates. Though high significant correlation coefficient was obtained between OM and aggregate stability by (Grieve (1980) and Mo lope et al. (1985) who worked on soils that varied in OC content from 5.1 - 11.5%. In contrast soils used for the study were low in OC content of which range between 0.10 - 0.8 (Table 4).

5. Conclusion

The findings of study showed that of all the aggregate stability indices used, both in wet and dry sieving in aggregate stability determination, texture was found to be a significant-controlling factor in both the aggregation formation and stability of soil aggregates. Among the soil textures, the MWD of the clay loam was significantly low under wet sieving, because it is prone to disintegration when wet and thus disappeared more easily into water than the other soils. The correlation of MWDD with MWDW, DA, SA was negative at the observed soaking periods. However, there was a significant correlation between MWDD, MWDW and DA at time 0mins. At time 90mins MWDD correlated significantly at $P < 0.05$ with MWDW and at 120 minutes MWDD also correlated significantly with MWDW, DA and SA. All these do confirm that period of soaking has effect on the stability of soil aggregates.

References:

1. Adesondun, J.K., Mbagwu, J.S.C. Oti, N., 2001. Structural stability and carbohydrate contents of an ultisol under different management systems, *Soil and Tillage Res.* 60: 235-142.
2. Albrecht, A., 1998. Le fractionnement granulometrique de la matiere organique appliqué a' la recherche de compartiments egregeants, le cas d'un vertisol sous pararie a la martineque 5^o Journees nationales de l' Etude des sols 22-25 avril 1996, Rennes France.
3. Amezketa, E., 1999. Soil aggregate stability. A review. *J. Sustain. Agric.* 14: 83-151.
4. Burke, W., Gabriel, D., Bourma, J., 1986. *Soil structure* AA Balkema publishers, the Netherlands.
5. Chisci, G., Bazzoffi, P., Mbagwu, J.S.C., 1989. Comparison of aggregate stability indices for soil classification and assessment of soil management practices, *Soil Tech.* 2:113-133.
6. Del Galdo, I., Six, J., Peressotti, A., Cotrufo, M.F., 2003. Assessing the impact of land use changes on soil C sequestration in agricultural soils by means of organic fractionation and stable C., isotopes GI. *Change B.* 9: 1204-1213.
7. Deneff, K., Six, J., (2005). Clay mineralogy determines the importance of biological versus abiotic processes for macro-aggregates formation and stabilization. *Europe. J. Soil Sci.* 65:468-479.
8. Deneff, K, Six, J., 2005. Clay mineralogy determines the importance of biological versus abiotic processes for macro-aggregate formation and stabilization. *Eur. J. soil Sci.* 56:469-479
9. Grieve, I.C., (1980). The magnitude and significance of soil structural stability declines under cereal cropping *CATENA* 7: 79-85
10. Igwe, C.A., Stahr, K., 2004. Water stable aggregates of flooded inceptisols from southeastern Nigeria in relation to mineralogy and chemical properties *Aust. J. Soil, Res.* 42;171-179.
11. Matkin, E.A., Smart, P., 1987. A Comparison of test structural stability. *J. Soil Science* 38: 123-135.

12. Mbagwu, J.S.C., 1992. A comparison of three micro-aggregation indices with other tests of structural stability, *Int'l Agrophysics* 6: 27-32.
13. Mo lope, M.B., Grieve, I.C., Page, B.R., 1985. Thioxotropic changes in the stability of molded soil aggregates, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 49: 970-983
14. Neaman, A., 2000. Rheological colloidal and physical chemical properties of standard palygorskite clay and of clays from palygorskite containing soil of the Jordan Valley, PhD. Thesis Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Faculty of Agriculture, Food and Environmental Quality Science, Rehovot, Israel.
15. Neaman, A., Singer, A., 2000. Kinetics of palygorskite hydrolysis in dilute salt solution, *Clay Mineral* 35:433-441.
16. Norton, L.D., Mamedox, A.I., Chi-hua, H., Levy, G.J., 2006. Soil aggregate stability as affected by long term tillage and clay mineralogy.
17. Nweke, I.A., Nnabude, P.C., 2015a. Colloidal stability and potential structural deformation index of four Nigerian soils, *Amer. J. Expt. Agric.* 5(2): 239-251.
18. Nweke, I.A., Nnabude, P.C., 2015b. Aggregate stability of four soils as evaluated by different indices, *J. Expt. Biol. Agric. Science* 3(3): 246-252.
19. Nweke, I.A., 2014. Changes in rheological properties of four contrasting soils as induced by cultivation. *J. Agric. Innov. Res.* 3(1): 373-378.
20. Nweke, I.A., 2000. Physical and chemical properties of aggregates of forested and cultivated soils in Nsukka area of southeastern, Nigeria, M.Sc. thesis department of soil science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria Pp 28-101.
21. Nweke, I.A., 2015. Effect of land use on organic matter concentration of aggregate fractions of fallow and cultivated soils, *Indian J. Appl. Res.* 5(3) 507-512.
22. Nweke, I.A., Nnabude, P.C., 2014. Aggregate size distribution and stability of aggregate fractions of fallow and cultivated soils, *J. Expt. Biol. Agric. Sci.* 1(7 special issue) 515-520.
23. Obi, M.E., 1990. A laboratory manual for soil physics Department of Soil Science University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria, Pp 9-13.
24. Piccolo, A., Mbagwu, J.S.C., (1994). Humic substances and surfactants effects on the stability of two tropical soils, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.* 58: 950-955
25. Piccolo, A., Mbagwu, J.S.C., (1999). Role of hydrophobic components of soil organic matter in soil aggregates stability, *Soil Sci. Am. J.* 63:1800-1810.
26. Six J., Elliot, E.T., Puastian, K., Combrink, C., 2000. Soil structure and organic matter I. Distribution of aggregate size classes and aggregate associated carbon. *Soil Science Society Am J.* 681-689.
27. Spaccini R., Zena, A., Igwe, C.A., Mbagwu, J.S.C., Piccolo, A., 2005. Carbohydrates in water stable aggregates and particle size fractions of forested and cultivated soils in two contrasting tropical ecosystems. *Kluwer Academic publishers*, printed in Netherlands, *Biogeochemistry* 53: 1-22.
28. Zhang B., Horn, R., 2001. Mechanism of Aggregate stabilization in Ultisols from subtropical China *Geoderma* 99:123-145.
29. Zhao, Y., Peth, S., Krummelbein, J., Horn, R., Wang, Z., Stefens, M., Hoffmann, C., Peng, X., 2007. Spatial variability of soil properties affected by grazing intensity in inner Mongolia grassland. *Ecological modelling* 205:241-254.